

Input-Output Analysis in Laptop Computer Manufacturing

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Abstract : The scope of this paper and the aim of proposed model were to apply monetary Input -Output (I-O) analysis to point out the importance of reusing know-how and other requirements in order to reduce the production costs in a manufacturing process for a laptop computer. I-O approach using the monetary input-output model is employed to demonstrate the impacts of different factors in a manufacturing process. A sensitivity analysis showing the correlation between these different factors is also presented. It is expected that the recommended model would have an advantageous effect in the cost minimization process.

Keywords : input-output analysis, monetary input-output model, manufacturing process, laptop computer

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